

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

IMPORTANCE OF LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE AND ROLE IN PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The article mentions the advantages of studying the English language in modern times and the fact that it plays an important role in the formation of a person's personality and personal development. The relevance of the English language grows every year. This is the main tool of communication in the international arena. Therefore, at any age, you should start studying and improving your knowledge, as the learning process in our country takes place throughout life. The modern world is strongly dependent on communication, especially in the context of international relations. English as the language of international communication provides a convenient platform for exchanging information and ideas. The topic is relevant today.

At all times, the main language in demand has been and remains English. According to many people, learning a foreign language is easy, because grammar and vocabulary are the basis for understanding it. In today's world, the knowledge and use of English is very important, because about 650 million people study it as an additional subject in educational institutions. That is why English is taught in almost all educational institutions of the country. We can say that English is more important than others. Since it is an international language, it should be known at least at a basic level. Today, people start learning English not only at school or university, but also at preschool institutions. It is important to understand that teaching this subject is carried out, first of all, for the development of a person, his personality, so that he can use these skills in his profession in the future [1].

In fact, many people do not understand how necessary a foreign language is in the 21st century. Nowadays, it is no secret that languages play a major role in employment. Most of the professions and positions are prestigious and highly paid, but this is only accompanied by knowledge of an additional language, mainly English. It cannot be said that this is how you can learn a language for yourself for the purpose of self-development and self-improvement. We live primarily for ourselves, which means we decide how we feel best. It is much more pleasant for anyone to talk about something with a foreigner than through an interpreter. After all, it will be a great experience in learning a foreign language.

In the world of high technologies, it is impossible not to notice the trend of development and creation of various inventions and programs. Most of them have foreign software and settings. Whether it's a laptop, tablet, phone, printer, or any program, all of them are originally foreign products, and even have foreign user manuals, mostly written in English. Therefore, everyone who wants to master the technique must know English [2].

Young people are the main category of people who know English fluently. Usually, this process takes place during the lesson in computer games. Teenagers spend a lot of time on the computer, and since all popular games are world hits, the manual is in English. Therefore, children unconsciously learn a foreign language without knowing it. Another way to learn a language is movies and music. Currently, the main product of consumption among young people is foreign films. They are very popular not only among European countries, but also in Kazakhstan. Most of them come in English format. The desire to hear and see something new drives young people to learn a language to understand what it is all about.

Learning English is not easy, but it is important both in everyday life and in science, technology and business, because it is an integral part of them. Most scientific research, technical publications and business documents are published in English. The advantages of learning English are many and we will give you some proofs to make it convincing:

➤ Global connectivity: the internet and social media have further connected the world, and knowing English allows us to actively participate in global dialogue, exchange ideas and share experiences.

➤ Education: many scientific studies, academic articles, books and online courses are available for reading in English. This allows us to learn directly from world experts, gain new knowledge and deepen our understanding of various fields.

➤ Career prospects: knowing English takes time and effort, but it becomes an important advantage in the job market. Expands the range of foreign jobs, opens opportunities to work abroad, cooperate with foreign colleagues and develop international business contacts.

➤ Developing personality and self-confidence: learning English requires perseverance, patience and self-discipline. This process contributes to our ability to overcome difficulties and achieve our goals [3].

Knowing a foreign language, getting to know the culture and traditions of other countries contributes to

development, and also allows you to communicate freely with people in any corner of the world. It is estimated that approximately one billion people worldwide use English as their mother tongue or as a foreign language. The use of English as an official or semi-official language is widespread in more than 70 countries and plays a very important role in another 20 countries. More than 1,400 million people live in countries where English is traditionally spoken. About 75% of the world's mail and information is stored in English. Most of the approximately 50 million Internet users use English.

I believe that English has a lot of potential as a future foreign language teacher. Training of the future teacher, in particular foreign language teacher, is based on the use of modern knowledge, methods and innovative technologies during the organization of professional training. In addition to mastering communicative competence in a foreign language, a foreign language teacher must have professional and general cultural competence. Learning a foreign language is in demand in the labor market, therefore, the training of specialists in the field of pedagogical education, in particular, in the field of teaching foreign languages, is of particular importance [4].

The main activity of the teacher is pedagogical communication. It is necessary to create a suitable atmosphere in the classroom in order to organize communication in order to encourage the student to share personal information with you, his opinion, his point of view. Pedagogical relationship usually means the professional relationship of a teacher with students in the process of education and training aimed at creating a favorable psychological climate and psychological optimization of general educational activities and relations between teachers and students. All professional functions are carried out in the framework of pedagogical relations, the main ones of which are teaching and education. The content of pedagogical communication includes the methods and skills of interaction between the teacher and the student team, which is the exchange of information, the demonstration of the educational effect and the organization of mutual understanding. The teacher acts as the initiator of this process, organizes and manages it [5].

These features impose a certain responsibility on the foreign language teacher, who must not only have a good linguistic knowledge and good methodological training, but also be an excellent speech partner who can convey his love for the language he teaches to the culture it offers. The teacher should be able to create an atmosphere of trust and comfort that promotes the motivation to study, the liberation of students, overcoming the language barrier, overcoming feelings of insecurity, the desire to communicate, and share their thoughts.

The teacher's role is this: organizing the foreign language learning process, talking on various topics, stimulating students' communication, he tries to instill in them moral qualities that are somehow related to the

content of the material read and discussed in class. The teacher strives to develop in students a sense of responsibility, respect for others, loyalty to work, pride in their country, people, culture and language, and at the same time to form a positive attitude towards foreign language culture. The educational possibilities of the subject, in addition to the content, are included in the methodological system of teaching and the teacher's personality and behavior. It is clear that the introduction of a text with learning opportunities into the textbook still does not give adequate results. It needs an appropriate interpretation and a teacher's attitude towards it. This teacher and his professional qualities (lesson planning, creative approach to the organization of communication, objective assessment and explanation of the student's answer, the ability to choose interesting materials and tasks) allow to direct the learning process in the right direction [6].

The best prerequisites for foreign language education are created when the teacher has experience in intercultural communication. The teacher's participation in international conferences, competitions and projects, publication in foreign magazines, active citizenship, professional development in the framework of seminars and courses, meetings of foreign delegations and the experience of a translator are invaluable, which can be used as an illustration of a certain aspect of the organization of intercultural communication, not only linguistic, but also cultural experience. lessons. Thus, modern teaching of foreign languages is connected with the reforms in the field of general education and the change of the paradigm of foreign language education. It is important to learn English, which has its own place in the world arena. I believe that it contributes to personal development and work.

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